

A KomaMRI Phantom Extension for Integrated Dynamic Imaging

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Synopsis (100/100words):

Motivation: KomaMRI is a newly released Pulseseq-compatible MRI simulator. Albeit the simulator includes dynamic imaging, motion type is limited to analytical expressions.

Goal: To provide KomaMRI with additional dynamic properties irrespective of the motion type.

Approach: To expand the phantom class to account for sampled arbitrary trajectories and to interpolate spin positions at time instants needed for the simulation. The simulation kernel is valid almost “as is” and only the demagnetization of the spins leaving the volume needs to be accounted for.

Results: 2D Cardiac cine with bright-blood effect, tagging and flow both with in-house and XCAT phantoms are dealt with now in KomaMRI.

Impact (40/40 words):

KomaMRI is expected to be used for designing and testing novel pulse sequences. The added capabilities provided by the extension we propose increase its potential associated by enabling the simulator to deal with any sort of motion for sequence design.

Main body (738/750 words without references)

Purpose:

KomaMRI¹, a Julia² package that simulates the MRI process, requires as input the definition of the phantom, the scanner and the sequence. The former contains information about each spin, namely, its initial position in the three axes and its magnetic properties (PD, T1 and T2). As for motion, it can be analytically defined using functions that are applied “on the fly” to all the spins in the volume. This method limits realistic motion simulation due to the difficulty of analytically defining realistic organ motion or flow models in closed-form expressions. Our purpose is to expand the phantom definition to accommodate realistic motion models in the simulator.

Methods:

To implement the phantom, we defined a new file format that extends its original definition. We also defined an interpolation mechanism, and slightly modified the simulation functions.

Phantom class extension:

A new motion model, referred to as *ArbitraryMotion*, has been included in the phantom for which closed-form expressions are no longer needed. Motion can now be expressed as a list of spin positions in space. Figure 1A shows the phantom structure. Displacements are stored in matrices Δx , Δy and Δz , with each row corresponding to a spin and each column to a discrete time instant. For periodic motion, parameter *dur* stores the cycle duration. Pseudo-periodic motion (such as arrhythmias) is accounted for by letting this parameter be a vector with different components. Each cycle is divided in K pieces, as illustrated in Figure 1B. Matrix *resetmag* contains flags that indicate when a reset in the magnetization of a spin should be carried out. This is necessary for simulating inflow and outflow of spins.

Interpolation:

Figure 1B shows how spin position is determined for each time step of the simulation. A piecewise linear interpolation is carried out, considering the Δx values (and similarly for the other two dimensions) as nodes. Interpolation is carried out in parallel prior to the simulation, since time instants are known and determined by the sequence. This pre-computed positions, and their corresponding *resetmag* flags, are passed to the actual simulation functions.

Simulation functions:

The phantom definition suits the current code since dynamic positions of the spin can be precomputed. Hence, only the magnetization state of the spins leaving the phantom volume must be reset. This is a straightforward operation in Julia due to its vector indexing capabilities.

Results:

Figure 2 shows a tagging-like acquisition carried out with a BSSFP sequence on a phantom with motion trajectories defined by analytical expressions but treated as expected in the *ArbitraryMotion* model. Figure 3 shows a cylindrical phantom in which particles that simulate blood spins are injected on in the left-hand side of the cylinder and move rightwards. Figures 3A and 3B show, respectively, a longitudinal and an axial slice of the cylinder where 2D cine is

simulated by means of the bSSFP sequence. Figure 3C shows the bright-blood effect encountered in 2D cine due to fresh blood particles entering the area where the steady state has already been reached by the spins on the myocardium. Finally, Figure 4 shows a cine image executed on an XCAT³ model where material point trajectories are expressed by a sequence of positions. Color images show the T1 (upper) and T2(lower) maps at end-diastole and end-systole (left and right respectively) and the image on the right-hand side shows the cine reconstruction.

Discussion:

KomaMRI indeed includes a dynamic model for phantom elastic motion; actually, the result in Figure 2 is obtainable with the original KomaMRI since spins motion is expressed by closed-form expressions. Other more involved motions per-se (Fig. 3) or motions obtained from external resources (such as XCAT) as a list of spatial positions (Fig. 4) require an extension such as the one we propose. We are aware of other simulators in which motion is also accounted for; one example is CMRSim⁴. The advantage of our model is that we have no difference in processing according to the type of motion we intend to simulate, since organ motion and flow (and, eventually diffusion) are handled similarly with minor changes in the simulation kernel functions. The downside of our approach is the amount of memory needed since, for the same number of spins, memory consumption increases to give room to the precalculated trajectories.

Conclusion:

KomaMRI has been extended to accommodate motion models for which an analytical closed form expression is not available. Future research will focus on improving the implementation of the model here proposed so that memory requirements are alleviated.

References:

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Figure 1. A) Phantom class structure. Most of the attributes of the phantom are arrays, in which each row corresponds to a spin. Initial positions (x , y , z) and contrast parameters (ρ , $T1$, $T2$) only need one-dimension arrays, while Δx , Δy , Δz and $resetmag$ need an additional dimension to account for the temporal evolution of positions and magnetizations. B) Interpolation method schema. The positions for the i -th spin in each simulation time step (referred to as $seqd.t$) are calculated by means of a piecewise linear interpolation. One cycle of duration dur and $K=4$ pieces is represented.

Figure 2. 2D cine tagging acquisition over a “hand-made” ring phantom, composed by 16108 spins and presenting contraction and expansion movements at 60bpm. Both A and B are made up of ten cardiac phases, each reconstructed with a 64x64 matrix. FOV = 15cm. The sequence used is a bSSFP with TR = 30ms and flip angle = 10°. Tagging is implemented by means of a simple SPAMM (1-1) sequence, prior to the bSSFP.

Figure 3. 2D cine acquisition over a cylindrical phantom of 17192 spins. Spins that simulate blood flow are injected on the left-hand side of the cylinder and move rightwards. All spins of the phantom have the same T1 = 1026ms and T2 = 42ms. Both reconstructions are composed of 10 32x32 matrices and are acquired by means of a bSSFP sequence: TR = 90ms, FOV = 4cm. Bright-blood effect can be observed as the animations progress. A) Longitudinal slice. B) Axial slice. C) Graphical representation of the bright-blood effect over time for two pixels: tissue (outer) and flow (inner).

Figure 4. A) T1 and T2 maps of a realistic moving heart phantom for $t = 0$ and $t = 0.5$ s. Displacements cause the spins to change positions and the spins are no longer equally spaced in a mesh pattern. This causes some undesired effects in the final cine, directly associated with the spin-level nature of the simulator. B) 2D cine acquisition over the heart phantom, composed by 10 cardiac phases of 64×64 pixels. The sequence is a bSSFP with $TR = 100$ ms and flip angle = 3° . Some artifacts appear due to the accumulation of spins in the compacted areas and their separation in the surroundings.